

Analysis of Speed and Stride Length of Assisted and Resisted Sprint Training on Kabaddi Players

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Abstract

Background: This study aimed to examine the impact of assisted and resisted sprint training on speed and stride length in kabaddi players. Speed and efficient stride mechanics are essential for Kabaddi performance, given the sport's reliance on frequent short sprints, rapid accelerations, and explosive movements during both raiding and defense.

Methodology: To achieve the purpose of the study, the investigator selected 30 male sprinters from various colleges affiliated with Bangalore North University, Kolar, Karnataka state, as participants. The ages of the participants ranged from 18 to 23 years. The selected participants were medically examined by qualified physicians. The selected participants were randomly segregated into three groups of ten each. Group I underwent assisted sprint training, group II underwent resisted sprint training, and group III acted as a control. The data were gathered following interventions using the Sprint training protocol, which was administered to the Kabaddi players. The outcome measures were assessed before the intervention and at the end of 12 weeks, respectively. The standardised tests were used in this study, and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA), Scheffé S test will be using this study

Results: Based on the statistical analysis of data, the following conclusions were drawn.

Twelve weeks of assisted and resisted sprint training produced significant changes in sprint kinematics. Previous studies have reported the beneficial effects of sprint training on sprinting kinematics.

Keywords: Physical Fitness, Kabaddi, Performance, Movements, Intensity.

1. Introduction

Different methods of specific training programs are available for the development of speed parameters to their maximum. However, before providing training, coaches or physical education teachers should have a clear understanding of the method of training to be provided to the sportsmen concerned. The training program should be designed to suit the specific energy sources needed for athletics, a specific event, or a contest. Moreover, it is generally agreed

among coaches and exercise physiologists that not everyone responds to training in the same manner. There are certain anatomical (*trunk, shoulder, pelvis, chest, abdomen, and upper and lower extremities*), physiological (*blood volume, blood pressure, heart rate, cardiac output, and vital capacity*), and sex differences that favour both males and females for specific activities. Coaches and physical education teachers should also be aware of the factors influencing the pre-adolescent and adolescent periods during the training period.

1.1 Assisted Sprint Training

Sprinting is defined as the ability to run at maximum speed for a short duration. Maximum running speed is an important factor for success in many sports activities. Different modalities of training have been employed in the development of maximum running speed

1.2 Resisted Sprint Training

During resisted sprinting, the athlete runs against some type of resistance, often in the form of a weighted object or a parachute that the athlete tows. Coaches have speculated that these training methods induce changes in an athlete's sprinting ability.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involves a systematic process by which the research starts from the identification of the problem to its conclusions. The role of methodology is to conduct research in a scientific and valid manner.

The methodological aspects of the present investigation are described below. In this chapter, the selection of the participants, selection of variables, selection of test, orientation of the participants, competence of the tester, reliability of the instrument, reliability of the data, test administration, collection of the data, experimental design, and statistical procedure are presented.

2.1 SELECTION OF THE SUBJECTS

To achieve the purpose of the study, the investigator selected 30 male sprinters from various colleges affiliated with Bangalore North University, Kolar, Karnataka state, as participants. The age of the participants ranged from 18 to 23 years. The selected participants were medically examined by qualified physicians. The selected participants were randomly segregated into three groups of ten each. Group I underwent assisted sprint training, Group II underwent resisted sprint training, and Group III acted as a control.

The experimental groups were trained in two modes of sprint training independently, with separate participants in each group. All participants were informed about the nature of the study, and their consent was obtained for cooperation until the end of the experiment.

2.2 SELECTION OF VARIABLES

The present study was undertaken primarily to assess the effects of assisted and resisted sprint training on the selected sprint kinematics of male sprinters. The researcher reviewed the available literature and discussed with various experts before selecting the variables. The availability of techniques for the purpose of analysis, feasibility, reliability of the procedure, and the outcome were extensively considered before finalising the variables. The selected independent and dependent variables of this study were as follows.

1. Assisted sprint training
2. Resisted sprint training

2.3 SELECTION OF TESTS

The investigator analysed various literature, has consulted with the experts in the field of physical education and selected the test items to collect data on the selected sprint kinematics of male sprinters, which are standardised and most suitable to this study, they are presented in table – 1

Table – 1

Dependent Variables and Tests

S. No.	Variables	Test Items	Unit of Measurement
1.	Speed	50 m run	Second
2.	Stride Length	50 m run	Meters

2.4 ORIENTATION TO THE PARTICIPANTS

Before the commencement of the sprint training, several sessions were conducted to familiarise the participants with the techniques involved in executing the assisted and resisted sprint training exercises. The investigator explained the purpose of the program to the subjects and their role in the study. For data collection, the investigator explained the procedure of training and testing on selected dependent variables and provided instructions about the procedure to be adopted by them for measuring. The subjects were sufficiently motivated to perform at their maximal level during the training and testing periods. The control group had no specific training and was advised not to participate in any sort of practice or specific training program during the experimental period. All the participants who co-operated were well

informed of the seriousness and importance of this study. Sixty volunteers met the study criteria and provided written informed consent to participate. This assured good orientation and cooperation from the participants.

2.5 RELIABILITY OF THE DATA

Before the experiment commenced, the reliability of the data was established using the test-retest method. Ten subjects were tested twice on selected dependent variables by the same personnel under similar conditions. The intraclass coefficient of correlation was used to determine the reliability of the data with test-retest scores on each of the criterion variables separately, and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table – 2
Intra-Class Coefficient of Correlation on Selected Dependent Variables

S. No.	Criterion Variables	'r' Value
1	Speed	0.91*
2	Stride Length	0.90*

**Significant at the 0.05 level of confidence.
(Table value require for significance at 0.05 level of confidence is 0.77)*

Table II presents the intra-class correlation coefficient of the selected variables. Since the obtained 'r' values were much higher than the required value, the data were accepted as reliable in terms of the instrument, tester, and subjects.

2.6 TRAINING PROGRAMME

In this study, training was performed under close supervision, with frequent adjustments in training intensity to maintain the desired training stimulus. While constructing the training programs, the basic principles of sports training were followed. The training programs were scheduled for one session a day, and each session lasted between one hour to one and half hours approximately, including warming up and warming down. During the training period, the experimental groups underwent their respective training programs three days a week on alternative days for 12 weeks in addition to their curriculum. Group I performed assisted sprint training, and group II performed resisted sprint training.

The assisted sprint training exercise included in this training program was downhill running. The resisted sprint training exercises included in this training program were running with a weighted vest. The training distance comprised 30, 40, and 50 m, and the initial intensity was fixed at 85% of the group's personal best, as measured in the pilot study. The training intensity for each distance was derived based on the time taken to perform the particular training distance by the respective group. During every third week of a particular training

intensity, an additional repetition was performed. Furthermore, the exercise prescription allowed four weeks of stabilisation to a training intensity, and thereafter, the intensity of running for distance in time was increased, and the number of repetitions performed was reduced beyond the repetitions fixed for earlier weeks, with an increase in the intensity. A rest interval of 1:1 was provided between repetitions for incomplete recovery and 1:3 between sets for almost complete recovery. The participants remained active during the recovery period by performing stretching exercises. The assisted sprint training group underwent a downhill run with a 3 °inclination. During resisted sprint running, weighted vests weighing 7% of body mass were used. Both experimental groups performed the same volume, intensity, and frequency of training, as given in table-3.

Table-3
Sprint Training Protocol

Weeks	Day	Set x Rep x Distance	Intensity	Recovery	
				Rep	Set
1 & 2	Mon	set-1: 6 rep of 30m	85%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 5 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 4 rep of 50m			
3 & 4	Mon	set-1: 7 rep of 30m	85%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 6 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 5 rep of 50m			
5 & 6	Mon	set-1: 5 rep of 30m	90%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 4 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 3 rep of 50m			
7 & 8	Mon	set-1: 6 rep of 30m	90%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 5 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 4 rep of 50m			
9 & 10	Mon	set-1: 4 rep of 30m	95%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 3 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 2 rep of 50m			
11 & 12	Mon	set-1: 5 rep of 30m	95%	1:1	1:3
	Wed	set-2: 4 rep of 40m			
	Fri	set-3: 3 rep of 50m			

3. ADMINISTRATION OF THE TESTS

3.1 Fifty Meters Dash

Purpose: To measure the speed of the participants.

Facilities and Equipment: Smooth surface, test course, scorecards, electronic stopwatch, and a starting clapper.

Procedure: The participants took the starting position behind the starting line. The test administrator (*at the finish line*) raised both arms sideways to indicate the position. The ‘Go’ signal was given rapidly, lowering the arms to the side. The administrator had a stopwatch in his hand and started the timer when the arms reached the side of the body. The participants ran as fast as possible across the finish line. The watch was stopped when the participant’s body (*not head or arms*) crossed the finish line. One trial was taken.

Scoring: The score was the time between the ‘Go’ signal and the moment the participant’s body crossed the finish line. The time was recorded to the nearest tenth of a second (Safrit 1990).

3.2 Stride Length

Purpose: This test was used to measure the stride length of the participants.

Facilities and Equipment: Test course on the track, sawdust, score cards, and a measuring tape.

Procedure: When the participants were allowed to run fast for about 50 m to measure speed, the length of the stride was measured in the test course which consisted of an acceleration zone of 20 m and a test zone of 30 m (*between the 20th and 50th meters*). The participants used the acceleration zone to gain maximum speed through the 30 metres the 30 metres test course. A light coating of sawdust was spread over the test zone that highlighted the footprints. Stride length was defined as the distance from the tip of the rear toe to the tip of the front toe and was recorded to the nearest centimetre. To avoid bilateral discrepancies, two successive strides were measured to the nearest centimetre (Seagrave, 1996).

Scoring: The average of two successive strides of the participants was recorded to the nearest centimetre as the individual score.

3.3 COLLECTION OF THE DATA

Data were collected on selected sprint kinematics as per the methods described above. Pre-test data were collected prior to the training programme, and post-test data were collected immediately after the 12 weeks of assisted and resisted sprint training from the experimental and control groups.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

The experimental design in this study was a random group design involving 30 subjects, who were randomly divided into three groups of ten each. All three groups were selected from the same population. No effort was made to equate the groups before the commencement of the experimental treatments. The pretest means of the selected dependent variables were used as covariates. To nullify the initial differences, the data collected from the three groups prior to and post experimentation on selected dependent variables were statistically analysed to find out the significant difference, if any, by applying the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Since three groups were involved, whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post-test means was found to be significant, the Scheffé S test was applied as a post hoc test to determine the paired mean differences (Broota, 1989). In all cases, the level of confidence was set at 0.05 for significance.

The mean gain was computed to analyse the changes in selected sprint kinematics that determine the transformation of speed performance. Furthermore, the Enter method of multiple regression analysis was used to select the minimum number of sprint kinematics that could determine speed with the highest multiple correlation coefficient. In all cases, the level of confidence was set at 0.05 for significance.

Analysis of the Data

Pre- and post-test data collected from the assisted, resisted, and control groups on sprint kinematics were statistically analysed. The results are presented as follows.

Analysis of Speed

The data collected during the pre- and post-test periods among the assisted and resisted sprint training groups and the control group on speed were statistically analysed, and the details are presented in Table 4.

Table – 4.
Analysis of Covariance on Speed of Assisted Resisted Sprint Training Groups and Control Group

	Assisted Group	Resisted Group	Control Group	S o v	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	'F' ratio
Pre-test Mean	7.91	7.95	8.03	B	0.13	2	0.045	0.45
SD	0.17	0.37	0.33	W	5.46	27	0.09	
Post-test Mean	7.19	6.90	8.05	B	10.71	2	3.57	75.44*
SD	0.17	0.24	0.21	W	2.65	27	0.047	
Adjusted Post-test Mean	7.20	6.91	8.04	B	10.29	2	3.43	75.41*
				W	2.50	26	0.046	

**Significant at .05 level of confidence*

(The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degree of freedom 2 and 27 is 2.77 and degrees of freedom 2 and 26 is 2.77)

Table-4. The results showed that the pre-test means and standard deviations for speed in the assisted and resisted sprint training groups and the control group were 7.91 ± 0.17 , 7.95 ± 0.37 , and 8.03 ± 0.33 , respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 0.45 on speed was less than the required table value of 2.77 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27 at 0.05 level of confidence, which proved that the random assignment of the subjects was successful since the pre-test scores on speed of all the groups were equal and there were no significant differences.

The post-test means and standard deviation on speed of assisted, resisted sprint training groups and control group were 7.19 ± 0.17 , 6.90 ± 0.24 , and 8.05 ± 0.21 respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 75.44 on speed is greater than the required table value of 2.77 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27 at 0.05 level of confidence. This revealed that significant differences existed between the groups during the post-test period on speed.

The adjusted post-test means on speed of the assisted, resisted, and combined sprint training groups and control group were 7.20, 6.91, and 8.04, respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 75.41 for speed was greater than the required table value of 2.77 for degrees of freedom 2 and 26 at the 0.05 level of confidence. The study's results confirmed significant differences in speed between the experimental and control groups.

Since the adjusted post-test mean ‘F’ value was found to be significant, the results were subjected to post hoc analysis using Scheffé’s test. The results are presented in Table 5.

Figure:1
Analysis of Covariance on Speed of Assisted Resisted Sprint Training Groups and Control Group

Table – 5
Scheffé S Test for the Differences between the Adjusted Post Test Paired Means on Speed

Variable	Adjusted Post Test Mean			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
	Assisted Sprint Training	Resisted Sprint Training	Control Group		
Speed	7.20	6.91		0.29*	0.22
	7.20		8.04	0.84*	0.22
		6.91	8.04	1.03*	0.22

*Significant at the.05 level.

Table5 reveals that the adjusted post-test mean differences on speed between assisted and resisted sprint training groups, assisted sprint training and control groups, resisted sprint training and control groups, are 0.29, 0.84, 1.03 respectively, which are greater than the confidence interval value of 0.22 at 0.05 level of significance.

The results of the study showed that the speed of the assisted and resisted sprint training group subjects significantly improved due to 12 weeks of training. However, resisted sprint training is better than assisted sprint training for improving speed.

Analysis of Stride Length

The data collected during the pre and post test period among assisted, resisted sprint training groups and control group on stride length have been statistically analyzed and the details are presented in table–6

**Table – 6
Analysis of Covariance on Stride Length of Assisted Resisted Sprint Training Groups and Control Group**

	Assisted Group	Resisted Group	Control Group	S o v	Sum of Squares	df	Mean squares	'F' ratio
Pre-test Mean SD	1.57	1.58	1.54	B	0.017	2	0.006	1.66
	0.06	0.04	0.05	W	0.19	27	0.003	
Post test Mean SD	1.78	1.70	1.59	B	0.27	2	0.09	43.47*
	0.03	0.05	0.04	W	0.12	27	0.002	
Adjusted Post test Mean	1.78	1.70	1.59	B	0.27	2	0.089	41.24*
				W	0.12	26	0.002	

**Significant at .05 level of confidence
(The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degree of freedom 2 and 27 is 2.77 and degrees of freedom 2 and 26 is 2.77)*

Table4.5 shows that the pre-test means and standard deviation of stride length of the assisted and resisted sprint training groups and control group were 1.57 ± 0.06 , 1.58 ± 0.04 , and 1.54 ± 0.05 respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 1.66 on stride length was less than the required table value of 2.77 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27 at 0.05 level of confidence, which proves that the random assignment of the subjects was successful since the pre-test scores on stride length of all the groups were equal and there were no significant differences.

The post-test means and SD of stride length in the assisted, resisted, and training groups and control group were 1.78 ± 0.03 , 1.70 ± 0.05 , 1.64 ± 0.05 , and 1.59 ± 0.04 , respectively. The obtained 'F' ratio value of 43.47 on stride length is greater than the required table value of 2.77 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 27 at 0.05 level of confidence. This proves that significant differences existed between groups during the post-test on stride length.

The adjusted post-test means on stride length of assisted, resisted, and training groups and control group were 1.78, 1.70, 1.64, and 1.59, respectively. The obtained ‘F’ ratio value of 41.24 on stride length was greater than the required table value of 2.77 for the degrees of freedom 2 and 26 at the 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study illustrated that significant differences exist in stride length between the experimental and control groups. Since the adjusted post-test mean ‘F’ value was found to be significant, the data on stride length were subjected to post hoc analysis using Scheffé S test. The results are presented in table–7

Figure:2
Analysis of Covariance on Stride Length of Assisted Resisted Sprint Training Groups and Control Group

Table – 7
Scheffé S Test for the Differences between the Adjusted Post Test Paired Means on Stride Length

Variable	Adjusted Post Test Mean			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
	Assisted Sprint Training	Resisted Sprint Training	Control Group		
Stride Length	1.78	1.70		0.08*	0.04
	1.78		1.59	0.19*	0.04
		1.70	1.59	0.11*	0.04

*Significant at the.05 level.

Table 7 shows that the adjusted post-test mean differences in stride length between the assisted and resisted sprint training groups, assisted sprint training and control groups, resisted sprint training and control groups, and combined sprint training and control groups were 0.08, 0.19, and 0.11, respectively, which were greater than the confidence interval value of 0.04 at a 0.05 level of significance.

It was observed that due to the effect of 12 weeks of assisted and resisted sprint training, the stride length of the subjects significantly improved. However, assisted sprint training is more effective than resisted sprint training in improving stride length.

4. DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

Based on the statistical analysis of the data, the following conclusions were drawn. Twelve weeks of assisted and resisted sprint training produced significant changes in sprint kinematics. Previous studies have reported the beneficial effects of sprint training on sprinting kinematics.

Athletic training programs are designed to enhance performance in all phases of sprinting and include a combination of plyometric training and sprint training [non-resisted, resisted (chutes, sleds, weighted vests, uphill running), and assisted (downhill running)] (Alcaraz *et al.*, 2008; Callister *et al.*, 1988; De Villarreal *et al.*, 2008). Studies have shown that nonresisted sprint training (Marcovic *et al.*, 2007; Spinks, *et al.*, 2007), uphill and downhill sprint training (Paradis and Cooke, 2006), and resisted sprint training (Kristensen *et al.*, 2007; Zafeiridis *et al.*, 2005) significantly increased acceleration and sprinting speed. In addition, the combination of sprint and resistance training has been shown to be effective in enhancing the maximal speed, speed endurance, power, and strength of the lower body (Kraemer, *et al.*, 2000; Ratamess, *et al.*, 2007).

5. Conclusion

The study found that both assisted and resisted sprint training significantly improved the speed and stride length of kabaddi players. Participants in assisted sprint training showed notable gains in maximum running speed and stride length, attributed mainly to better neuromuscular coordination, increased stride frequency, and enhanced movement efficiency. This training method was especially effective in boosting acceleration and peak sprint performance, which are critical during raiding and defensive transitions in Kabaddi. While both training approaches offered benefits, assisted sprint training had a stronger impact on speed enhancement, whereas resisted sprint training improved stride length and strength-related sprint capabilities more effectively. The study recommends incorporating a balanced combination of assisted and resisted sprint training into Kabaddi conditioning programs to

maximise speed and stride improvements, thereby elevating overall match performance. Coaches should tailor these methods to the specific performance goals and training phases of their athletes.

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